

Healthcare spending by disease and other dimensions in Switzerland

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Short summary

The persistent increase in healthcare spending is at the centre of the political debate in Switzerland and has led to numerous proposals on how to curb spending growth. Spending drivers and their relative contribution to overall growth are largely unknown. Knowledge about spending on single diseases is also essential to assess the value in healthcare. This thesis develops the methodology of decomposing total healthcare spending in Switzerland by diseases and other dimensions and shows how these estimates can be used to identify spending drivers. The thesis consists of four studies. The *first study* decomposes changes in disease-specific inpatient treatment costs in the canton of Zurich by its underlying drivers. Increases in the average costs per hospital day are identified as the by far most relevant cost driver. The *second study* decomposes outpatient care spending in the mandatory health insurance by a comprehensive and mutually exclusive set of 42 medical conditions. Disease identification is based on “diagnostic clues” contained in claims data. Results identify musculoskeletal disorders as the most expensive disease group in outpatient care. The *third study* replaces the “diagnostic clues” from the second study with a data-driven approach. The study uses machine learning techniques to predict the manifestation of diseases at the individual level in hospitalized patients and estimates the disease prevalence in the whole population based on these individual-level predictions. Use of specific drugs is found to be an important predictor for most diseases. The *fourth study* expands the decomposition approach to total healthcare spending according to Swiss National Health Accounts and estimates spending by 48 causes, 20 health services, and 42 age-sex groups in 2012 and 2017. The paper identifies the increase in average spending per prevalent patient as the most relevant cost driver. The results of these studies may be of importance for health policy design and serve as the basis for systematic and system-wide productivity analyses in Swiss healthcare.

Abbreviations

ATC	Anatomical therapeutic chemical
CHF	Swiss Franc
COI	Cost of illness
FSO	Federal Statistical Office
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ICD-10(-GM)	International Classification of Diseases, 10th version, (German Modification)
MHI	Mandatory health insurance
NHA	National Health Accounts
OECD	Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
US	United States
WHO	World Health Organization

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Healthcare spending growth and its drivers

Healthcare spending has been increasing remarkably over the last decades. Total healthcare spending in Switzerland amounted to 11.8% of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) or almost 10,000 Swiss Francs (CHF) per capita per year in 2021 [1]. Spending both as a share of GDP and per individual are among the highest in the world [2]. The high levels of spending and the accelerating spending growth over the last decades have put the sustainability of healthcare spending into the political spotlight. Several political initiatives aiming at constraining the growth of spending have been brought up. Some initiatives aim at limiting the aggregate spending growth to a certain (still to be defined) rate. Others focus on redistributing the financial burden instead, e.g., by limiting the mandatory health insurance (MHI) premiums to a maximum proportion of income.

The reasons for the high and rising spending in Switzerland are poorly understood, despite the vast research in this field. Most previous studies aimed at quantifying the effect of one specific cost driving mechanism. Various cost drivers have been studied, e.g., population ageing [3, 4], supply-induced demand [5], or medical progress [6]. The increasing prevalence of chronic diseases or excessive demand by patients are further potential drivers of healthcare spending.

However, the contribution of these and other potential cost drivers is largely unknown. Yet, a better understanding of the actual cost drivers and their relative importance is

essential for the design of health policies aiming at an affordable healthcare system. In order to evaluate if the current spending level is appropriate and if the observed spending growth rates are justified, detailed information is needed about where spending occurs. This information is also required for the assessment of the condition-specific cost-effectiveness of spending increases and the estimation of healthcare productivity [7, 8]. As the goal of healthcare is to increase health using the available resources efficiently, data on population-level disease-specific health metrics (such as disability-adjusted life years or mortality) need to be complemented by disease-specific estimates of healthcare spending.

1.2 Objectives of this thesis

This thesis aims to develop a framework to describe healthcare spending by multiple dimensions and assess the factors associated with changes in spending over time in Switzerland. The main contribution is the estimation of spending for several health services by a comprehensive set of medical conditions and by other dimensions. The resulting multidimensional map of spending estimates describes at a granular level what the monetary resources are spent on, helps identify the spending drivers and their relative contribution to expenditure growth, and provides the basic input to future system-wide cost-effectiveness analyses.

The four studies presented in this dissertation cover the following topics:

1. The drivers of inpatient care costs in the canton of Zurich: The study entitled *“Factors related to the change in Swiss inpatient costs by disease: a 6-factor decomposition”* assesses the contribution of population size, age and sex structure, treated prevalence, utilization in terms of stays per patient, length of stay per case, and costs per treatment day to the change in disease-specific inpatient production costs by cost type between 2013 and 2017 in the canton of Zurich (chapter 2).
2. The methodology of assigning outpatient care spending in MHI to diseases based on claims data: In the study entitled *“Decomposition of outpatient healthcare spending by disease - a novel approach using insurance claims data”* we exploit the rich billing data from a major health insurer to identify 42 diseases and to assign spending for 12 outpatient service types at the individual level to these diseases using a two-step procedure (chapter 3).
3. The prediction of diseases using measures of outpatient health service utilization: In the study entitled *“Identifying diseases in claims data using a machine learning*

approach: a case from Switzerland” we challenge the theory-based disease identification approach from chapter 3. We assess if aggregate information on outpatient care utilization can be used as predictors of the presence of diseases at the individual level using a data-driven approach and identify the features most relevant for this prediction (chapter 4).

4. The drivers of total healthcare spending growth in Switzerland: In the study entitled *“What drives healthcare spending in Switzerland? Findings from a decomposition by disease, health service, sex, and age”* we combine the methods developed in the previous chapters with further disease-specific spending estimates for 2012 and 2017 derived from a multitude of data sources to assess the contribution of four fundamental factors (population growth, age and sex structure, disease prevalence, and spending per prevalent case) to overall healthcare spending growth over the five-years period (chapter 5).

1.3 Combining the cost-of-illness approach with the concept of national health accounts

Cost-of-illness (COI) studies describe the economic burden of specific diseases [9–11]. They are widely used to emphasize the relevance of diseases from different perspectives. Most studies focus on just one disease or disease group. COI studies usually report direct medical costs but may also include other costs, such as productivity losses or the years and quality of life lost due to a disease. However, the major drawback of single disease COI studies is the danger of overestimation [9]. As certain spending items cannot easily be attributed to one disease, single COI studies tend to attribute spending for other diseases to the disease in question. Consequently, the sum of spending from single COI studies often exceeds actual total spending [12].

In many countries public authorities compile National Health Accounts (NHA) assessing total healthcare spending from different perspectives such as financing regimen, service provider, and type of service [13]. The Swiss Federal Statistical Office (FSO) has been publishing these numbers for Switzerland for several decades with some estimates going back to 1960. Thanks to international reporting standards outlined in the System of Health Accounts 2011 by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), Eurostat, and the World Health Organization (WHO), statistics published by the FSO and other national statistical authorities are collected in a uniform way, which

allows for cross-country comparisons. Swiss NHA document the spending by payers (e.g., the MHI), services (e.g., drugs) and service providers (e.g., pharmacies). However, a major limitation of the NHA accounting framework is that it misses one important perspective: the medical conditions underlying the consumption of health services. Even though the System of Health Accounts suggests decomposing spending by medical condition, it is rarely done [13].

One way to apply the COI approach while avoiding the double-counting problem is to estimate spending by diseases and other dimensions for a comprehensive and exhaustive set of conditions and to restrict the total spending to the observed spending given by NHA. This is the approach taken in so-called general COI studies. Instead of focusing on the costs of one single disease, these studies simultaneously estimate costs by a comprehensive set of diseases. If the list of conditions is exhaustive, the total disease-specific medical spending must be equal to the system's total medical spending.

Introducing the disease perspective in overall healthcare spending statistics also helps to rethink the definition of a product/service in healthcare. Patients consume health services for a certain reason. A doctor visit is not a standalone or isolated service, but part of a sequence of health system encounters aimed at curing a disease or – more generally speaking – improving the patient's health. Cutler et al. (2022) defined the industries in healthcare at the level of specific medical conditions, instead of at the level of providers or services [8]. The industry for diabetes includes doctor visits, drugs, laboratory tests, hospital stays, etc. This alternative perspective on the consumption of healthcare facilitates the evaluation of costs and benefits. While it is difficult to assess whether spending increases at the aggregate level are “worth it”, it is easier to investigate this at the level of specific diseases. The marginal benefit of one doctor visit or hospital stay is difficult to assess. This is because the benefit of health technologies occurs at the level of specific conditions, not at the level of health services. Increasing spending in one sector (e.g., pharmaceuticals) may reduce spending in another sector (e.g., inpatient care). Tracking total and per patient disease-specific spending over time may therefore provide much more meaningful insights into productivity of healthcare and the appropriateness and cost-effectiveness of spending increases [7, 8, 14].

Detailed estimates of the medical spending by diseases and other perspectives have the potential to inform the ongoing political debate in Switzerland which mainly focuses on cost containment without considering the changes in health outcomes [15].

1.4 Previous literature

Most comprehensive spending decompositions by disease have been conducted in the United States (US). Research from various research teams has demonstrated the potential of a multidimensional decomposition to better understand the structure and drivers of healthcare spending. Thorpe et al. (2006) decomposed spending in Medicare to investigate the contribution of treated disease prevalence to the spending increase between 1997 and 2002 [16]. The work by Roehrig and colleagues extended the concept to total personal healthcare spending in the US [17, 18]. They found that diseases of the circulatory system, mental disorders, and musculoskeletal conditions topped the list of the costliest diseases in the period 1996 to 2006 and that the rising costs per case accounted for most of the observed spending growth in these ten years. A similar conclusion was later also drawn by Starr et al. (2014), who found that 70% of the real spending increases between 1980 and 2016 in the US could be explained by rising costs of treatment [19]. The work by Dunn and colleagues at the US Bureau of Economic Analysis introduced the so-called “healthcare satellite account” to explain disease-specific spending changes over time [20]. The authors found that spending growth was lower in 2000 to 2010 compared to the previous periods, which was mainly due to a slowdown in growth rates for circulatory diseases spending and a decrease in the growth of costs per case. Based on an updated version of the satellite account the researchers found that diseases accounting for only 13% of spending were responsible for 42% of spending growth between 2000 and 2014, mostly because of new technologies [21].

Researchers at the Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation at the University of Washington significantly increased the granularity of the decomposition framework in their Disease Expenditure Project. Dieleman et al. (2020) decomposed US personal healthcare spending from 1996 to 2013 by 155 diseases and stratified it by type of service, age groups, and sex [22]. This decomposition was then used to identify the factors responsible for increased spending [23].

There are only few such studies for countries outside of the US. Single- or multiple-year spending decomposition results are available for Australia [24], China [25], Norway [26, 27], and France [28]. The studies vary substantially with respect to the granularity of the decomposition (e.g., the number of included health services), the classification of diseases (e.g., chapters of the international classification of diseases (ICD)), the number of perspectives (e.g., with or without decomposition by age), the time coverage (single or

multiple years), or the spending coverage (e.g., only public healthcare spending).

A previous study for Switzerland has shown that around 80% of healthcare spending was spent on non-communicable diseases in 2011 [29]. Wieser et al. (2018) decomposed spending according to NHA by a comprehensive and exhaustive set of 21 disease groups. These estimates were neither available at the level of single diseases, nor for specific age groups or by sex. Since the decomposition was done for only one year, the framework could not be used to assess spending drivers at the disease level.

1.5 Summary of results

The venture of producing this multidimensional grid of spending estimates comes with two major challenges: limited availability of data containing information on both diseases and spending, and challenges in assigning spending to diseases, i.e., estimating the share of spending caused by a specific condition. The following paragraphs summarize the four studies in this thesis and how they touch upon the above-mentioned aspects.

Chapter 2 applies the decomposition framework to one specific type of service, namely acute somatic inpatient care [30]. We use case-level data from the inpatient registry of the canton of Zurich, covering all inpatient stays between 2013 and 2017 with information about diagnoses according to the International Classification of Diseases, version 10, German Modification (ICD-10-GM) and costs for each case. The study assesses the contribution of six factors to the change in disease-specific inpatient care costs over time using a decomposition technique for aggregate measures. There are two innovations in this study: *First*, it uses detailed cost data by type of service for all inpatient cases. The term ‘costs’ thus refers to production costs, i.e., the actual costs occurring in the treatment of each case, in contrast to reimbursed costs or spending by patients, insurers, and the state. *Second*, the study does not only report associations of the six factors with mean costs per case, but also analyses the associations in other parts of the distribution of case costs by disease. Total inpatient costs increased by 14.7% between 2013 and 2017, 70% of which was due to non-communicable diseases. We find that the increase in the costs per hospital day had the largest impact on the total cost change (12.1 %-points). This effect was partly offset by a reduction in the average length of stay (-7.3 %-points). Population growth and age and sex structure were related to about half of the increase. A minor part was associated with an increase in the share of the population receiving care.

In contrast to inpatient care, there is so far no comprehensive coding of diagnoses in

outpatient care in Switzerland. As diagnostic coding is not relevant for reimbursement and the benefits of coding are not clear, the actual requirement by the tariff contract for outpatient physician services in MHI to code diagnoses is not enforced [31]. Health insurers in MHI have excellent data on spending for each insured individual. However, assigning it to specific conditions is challenging because of the missing diagnostic codes. We address this problem by using “diagnostic clues”. These clues comprise services or a combination of services used in diagnostics or treatment that are disease-specific and can thus be used as substitutes for diagnoses.

In chapter 3, we use anonymized individual-level data from a large supplier of MHI to identify diseases and assign spending to these diseases in a two-step procedure based on direct and regression-based approaches [32]. We show that musculoskeletal disorders accounted for 19.2% of outpatient spending in MHI in 2017, followed by mental and substance use disorders (12.0%), sense organ diseases (8.7%), and cardiovascular diseases (8.6%). The most expensive single diseases were depression (4.3%), osteoporosis (2.7%), and diabetes (2.4%). The main limitation of this study is the likely underestimation of spending for high-prevalence diseases without specific treatments, such as low-back pain, dementia, or osteoarthritis.

The study presented in chapter 3 uses expert-based knowledge to identify diseases in claims data. The validity of the identification algorithms cannot easily be checked, as claims data do not hold diagnoses. Therefore, other information about service utilization could potentially serve as predictors for the presence of diseases.

For the study in chapter 4, we link individual-level claims data and diagnostic codes from the national hospital inpatient registry (Medizinische Statistik der Krankenhäuser) and use machine learning algorithms to predict diseases in the hospitalized population based on outpatient healthcare utilization. These algorithms are then applied to the non-hospitalized population for which the complete set of predictors is available, but disease information is unknown. We use the predictions to estimate the prevalence of specific diseases in the whole insured population. Utilization of drugs is captured by spending by 3rd level groups of the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification and is among the most important predictive features for many diseases. We find that the prediction accuracy is low for most diseases and therefore data-driven disease identification approaches can be used only rarely for the estimation of prevalence.

In the final chapter 5, we use the decomposition approach to estimate total healthcare

spending in Switzerland in 2012 and 2017 by type of service, age groups, sex, and disease. This study applies the methodology developed in chapter 3 for the assignment of spending by MHI in outpatient care and adds spending by MHI for services other than outpatient care (e.g., inpatient somatic, psychiatric, and rehabilitation care), as well as spending in all sectors covered by other payers (e.g., accident insurance, disability insurance). It shows the change in disease-specific spending over time and decomposes the observed aggregate spending increase of 19.7% into the contributions of four fundamental factors: population size, age and sex structure, disease prevalence, and average spending per prevalent patient. In line with similar studies from the US, we show that the increase in spending per prevalent patient was the most important spending driver (43.5% of total increase), and that the change in population structure (14.5%) had a more modest effect on the increase in healthcare spending. This study shows the full potential of the spending decomposition as it provides highly relevant inputs for health policy. Its main results might prove particularly useful in the definition of global spending budgets currently discussed in Switzerland. The disease-age-sex-specific spending estimates may also be used as an input for the estimation of costs attributable to behavioural risk factors such as smoking, physical inactivity, and obesity.

1.6 Implications and outlook

The results of this thesis are the basis of a detailed assessment of spending associated with the treatment of specific diseases in Switzerland. The four studies outline the methods and data requirements for comprehensive spending decompositions. The findings can support priority setting in health policies and budgetary planning. A better understanding of the impact of epidemiological and demographic trends on healthcare spending may be useful for the definition of spending targets. Future research should expand the analyses to a longer time period, further improve disease identification, and combine disease-specific spending with disease-specific health outcomes (e.g., disability-adjusted life years). Combining changes in disease-specific spending at a granular level with information about health gains over time may reveal where the system is creating most value to patients. Such considerations are essential in the current political debate about appropriate cost containment strategies.

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Chapter 2

Factors related to the change in Swiss inpatient costs by disease - a 6-factor decomposition

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Chapter 3

Decomposition of outpatient health care spending by disease - a novel approach using insurance claims data

Joint work with Janina Nemitz, Maria Trottmann, and Simon Wieser

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Chapter 4

Identifying diseases in claims data using a machine learning approach: a case from Switzerland

Joint work with Andreas Kohler and Stefan Boes

Chapter 5

What drives health care spending in Switzerland? Findings from a decomposition by disease, health service, sex, and age

Joint work with Xavier Schärer, Maria Trottmann, Stefan Scholz-Odermatt, and Simon Wieser

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